

Analysis of Sastra dan Kuliner : Evolusi Gastronomi ke Gastrosofi dalam Tiga Cerpen Indonesia By Bramantio

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Abstract

The purpose of the paper analysis is “Filosofi kopi” and “Madre” by Dee and “Sokol” by Nukila Amal are short stories that present culinary as a generator of its structures. Coffe, starter dough, and smokol (brunch in the tradition of Manado people) are not merely food and beverage. In the beginning, the stories seem to tell about the celebration of life, the efforts to get the best presentation and taste of food and beverage, and the understanding of personal identity, but then move into another direction, a point named contemplation of Indonesia. Those short stories are miniatures of Indonesia, itsIndonesiains Indonesia is not the collapsed and gloomy one, but Indonesia with a better future because it has Ben, Tansen, and Batara as an urban young generation with awareness to accept, explore, and maintain their ancestor’s philosophical values.

Keywords: *starter dough, coffee, connotation, culinary, smoko*

INTRODUCTION

“ Coffee philosophy,” tells, a piece about journey life figure named Ben dan Café named Coffee Philosophy, short stories told through corner corners look at jody as a friend at a time colleague work and the owner of the coffee philosophy capital focus on fall Wake up their living shop and find concoction best. Same with " The Coffee Philosophy ", the short story "Madre" tells the story of several weeks crucial in life figure named Tansen, begins with will Tansen being involved in history long batter prick named Madre who has 70 years old. The same nuance is also found in the short story " Sokol", a short story duration short compared with two short stories previously that make a man named Batara aka Batre as axis a story that has a playground named smoko.

A single artifact can give rise to several aesthetic objects and it depends entirely on the reader and the way a reader is an aesthetic object, “Coffee Philosophy”, “Madre”, and “readingSokolg”

worship signs that need to be interpreted. Literary work consists of two poles, namely artistic and aesthetic. Semiotics postulates a relationship between two terms, signifier and signified, that relationship relates to objects belonging to different categories and therefore the relationship is not equivalent but equivalence.

METHOD

This study of analysis uses a descriptive qualitative method because it explains a social event for how the writer uses for analyzing the paper. The writer sees this method to be very important because this method will show a form of explanation related to a phenomenon that is interpreted in the context and concept of writing. Of course, in carrying out this research, the author uses a hermeneutic approach because this paper analysis will be studied by exegesis of the contents and adjusting to the events that occurred at that time. The theory is used in literature and reading creation literature. Creation literature not only applies as artifacts but at a time as object aesthetic. Artifact is object material base aesthetic, while object aesthetics is representation artifact in thought reading.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The findings in this study are The short story “ Philosophy of Coffee”, via corner look future character is known named jody, opened with a story about the love a figure named ben against coffee. Since e beginning has been known been the ups and downs café was later determined by Ben as the party who owns knowledge about coffee and method processing. a t story “Madre” opened withTheThewshorte the s rta short ory about death that makes confused si a storyteller named Tansen.

When Tan Sin bequeath batter prick named Madre to Tansen, who in then day associate it with two bakery lwgwndaris Tan De Bakker and Fairy Bakery. The short story “ Smokol ” begins with that description too beneficial as an introduction by direct about what, how, and who only told in a short story that is Becomes focus story is smoko, Batara and third his friend. Sokol as a tradition in veon original put supporters on position stories of no distance from him, smool simply habit eat in Among breakfast and eat noon.

The purpose of this analysis of papers in the form of discussions is “ Coffee Philosophy ”, “Madre”, and “Sokolare short stories that present food and drink or culinary as the focus the the stories. Coffee, dough prick named Madre, dan smoko Becomes determinant motion figure central short story the in finding Streetlife they.“ Coffee Philosophy ”, “Madre”, and “ Sokol ” which originally looks as piece story Ben's life together with the coffee, Tansen together batter the culprit, and God together smolnya could draw b para figure and culinary.

As stated by Batara, gastronomic truth is someone who understands that all food is a blessing and not contain Thing bad During no eaten excess. Various enjoyment for tongue in the short story the no just understood in level fulfillment primary needs. The third short story the with the method each aims more targets _ big than serving in glass and plate in on table eat, namely Indonesia.

CONCLUSION

How the writer subjectively sees from the paper analysis that Works literature in his visible form simple even though always keeps layer overcharge structure the surface. The story in Creation literature is always realized by imaging “ Philosophy of Coffee”, “Madre” by Dee, and “ Sokol ” Karya Nuclear Amel offer a basic poetry self on culinary. Finally could declare that “Coffee Philosophy ”, “Madre”, and “ Sokol ” become a kind of miniature Indonesia.

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